

Moderating Effect of Bank Size on Relationship between Financial Innovations Adoption and Financial Deepening of Listed Commercial Bank in Kenya

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Abstract

Despite commercial entities amplifying financial innovation there is need for empirical inquiry on their contributions towards economic development through financial inclusion and deepening. Financial deepening is the capacity of financial institutions to enhance access to its services. Financial innovations have reduced turnaround time for banking services such as withdrawals, deposit and loan approval process. Despite this documented evidence its contribution to economic development through financial deepening is barren empirical ground. Hence, this paper investigated the relationship between financial innovations adoption and financial deepening of listed commercial banks in Kenya. The study was anchored on technology acceptance model. Expo facto research design was adopted, census of 12 listed commercials was considered for five years. A significant relationship between financial banking innovations and financial deepening was reported. Also, there was significant moderating effect of bank size on the relationship between financial innovations adoption and financial deepening of listed commercial banks.

Keywords: Financial innovations, Financial deepening, bank size

Introduction

Traditionally innovation was perceived as cost minimization strategy, risk reduction, market penetration and service efficiency enhancement and amplified commercial entity growth (Francesca & Claeys, 2010). The situations have been altered since its currently viewed owing to a sporadic and turbulent business environment that has altered commercial entities' performance targets (Gardachew, 2010). Through financial products engineering, business dynamism response can be easily managed. According to Henderson & Pearson (2011) there are chances of information asymmetry, which may create chances of business losses but through technological innovations due diligence prior to commercial enterprise engagement can be easily evaluated. Despite commercial entities amplifying financial innovation there is need for empirical inquiry on their contributions towards economic development through financial inclusion and deepening.

Financial deepening is the capacity of a financial institution to enhance access to its services. According to Omwansa and Waema (2014) growth of telecommunication and mobile phones penetration has amplified financial deepening especially amongst those who were unbanked and those who earn their living in the informal sector. Financial inclusion is a relatively new terminology that refers to the process or methods by which financial service options are made available, at reasonably affordable costs or free of charge, to persons who are mainly bottom of the pyramid, that traditional financial channels have a lesser interest in delivery to; via institutionalized and rigid structures, low returns and/or the modus operandi of financial service providers (Hannig & Jansen, 2010). Financial system development is attributed to its ability to bridge the gap between deficit saving units and surplus units and introduction of non-banked population to banking services.

Innovation in banking sector lead to operational costs reductions and enhanced customer satisfaction; this is due to amplification on banking services access upon adoption of digital financial products. It has been argued that unless commercial banks adopt digital financial products then there are low chances of enhancing their performance and retaining their customers since there will exude to those institutions which have incorporate innovations in their strategic plans (Jegade, 2014). This can only through the continued interrelationship between all stakeholders such as regulatory institutions and political elite who are bestowed with the responsibility of legalizing banking operating guidelines through passing of relevant legislations.

Mwangi (2013) argued in favour of considering customers' interest whenever developing innovative products because, despite the turbulence of the business environment, the adoption of new innovation is paramount for its success. Similar, arguments were put forth by Joshua (2010) who argued that net present value of investment project could only be achieved through incorporation of all stakeholder's interest and in situations where commercial banks are driven by desire to enhance efficiency they must consider customer needs and ease of using new development.

In Kenya the situation on financial innovation has intense competition from telecommunication communications such as Safaricom M-pesa services. This innovation is credited for it's easy to use human user interface and due to this, it has escalated financial innovation to the extent of creating overdraft facility for its users. According to Weil, Mbiti and Mwege (2012) financial innovations have reduced turnaround time for banking services such as withdrawals, deposit and loan approval process. Despite this documented evidence, its contribution to economic development through financial deepening is barren empirical ground. Hence, this paper investigated the relationship between financial innovations adoption and financial deepening of listed commercial banks in Kenya.

General Objective

The general objective of this study was to analyze the relationship between financial innovations adoption and the financial deepening of listed commercial banks in Kenya.

Specific Objectives

Specifically, the following objectives guided the study:

- i. To determine the relationship between mobile phone banking and the financial deepening of listed commercial banks in Kenya.
- ii. To examine the relationship between ATM banking and financial deepening of listed commercial banks in Kenya.
- iii. To establish the relationship between online banking and financial deepening of listed commercial banks in Kenya.
- iv. To find out the relationship between agency banking and financial deepening of listed commercial banks in Kenya.
- v. To determine the moderating effect of bank size on the relationship between financial innovations adoption and financial deepening of listed commercial banks in Kenya.

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were adopted in the study:

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between mobile phone banking and the financial deepening of listed commercial banks in Kenya.

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between ATM and the financial deepening of listed commercial banks in Kenya.

Ho₃: There is no significant relationship between online banking and the financial deepening of listed commercial banks in Kenya.

Ho₄: There is no significant relationship between agency banking and the financial deepening of listed commercial banks in Kenya.

Ho₅: There is no significant moderating effecting of bank size on the relationship between financial innovation and financial deepening of listed commercial banks in Kenya.

Empirical and Theoretical Review

Theoretical Review

Technology Acceptance Model

This was developed by (Davis, 1989). The theory supports the use of technology to enhance service delivery. Its anchored-on aspects such as "perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use and perceived enjoyment" while using it. Successful adoption of technology is based on organization capacity to address customer's unique needs (Pedersen, Leif, Methlie and Thorbjornsen, 2002). Incorporation of Automatic Teller Machines by commercial

banks ought to be addressing customer needs. There is need for its continued development and interlinking with alternative technological development.

The theory is relevant in the study since the incorporation of online banking in provision of banking services has not only enhanced banking performance but amplified the state of financial deepening.

Empirical Review

A Bangladesh examination of role of mobile banking on financial performance was put forth by (Rayhan, Sohel, Islam & Mahjabin, 2012). The descriptive research design was adopted and purposive sampling applied to select respondents. A semi-structured questionnaire was adopted to gather primary data. Quantitative data was analyzed using classical regression modelling. It was found that mobile banking had significant positive effect on access to banking services, which increased their market share. Increased market share through mobile banking could signal positive impact on financial inclusion and deepen. Since Bangladesh and Kenya are in different states of economic development, study findings in Bangladesh cannot be generalized in Kenya hence the need to customize an empirical enquiry. Furthermore, use of purposive sampling to select respondents would have created possibilities of biased selection of respondents.

Al-Jabri (2012) investigated the effect of mobile banking technological adoption on commercial banking performance in Saudi Arabia. Specifically, the study investigated what inhibits or promotes mobile banking. The qualitative and quantitative research design was adopted. Primary data was collected through interview guides and structured questionnaires. It was found that success of mobile banking was dependent on telecommunication penetration, quality network, availability of mobile phones. Technical awareness of respondents impacted penetration of mobile banking. These findings may not be generalized in Kenya since the state of mobile penetration may not be the same. Also, the study limited its inferential statistics to correlation and regression. It would have been appropriate to incorporate structural equation modelling.

Adewoye (2013) investigated the effect of Automated Teller Machine (ATM) on commercial banking performance in Nigeria. The descriptive research design was adopted. Primary data was collected through use of questionnaires amongst respondents who were drawn purposively. Inferential and descriptive statistics were adopted to analyze the data. It was found that ATM impacted positively on quality of services accorded to commercial banks customers.

Mwatsika (2016) investigated the effect of ATM on banking customer's satisfaction in Malawi. The descriptive research design was adopted. Stratified sampling was used to select respondents whom questionnaires were administered. Inferential and descriptive statistics were used to analyse the data. It was found that ATM impacted customer satisfaction positively. Through ATM, commercial banks were able to cannibalize each other and this triggered innovative ways of attracting and retaining customers. This enhanced access to commercial banking services. It would have been appropriate to blend quantitative data with qualitative, which would have been gathered through use of interview guides and focus group discussion. In addition to classical regression modelling, structural regression model ought to have been adopted so to examine the strength of contribution of each construct.

Hasan et al. (2012) investigated the effect of internet banking on commercial banking in Italy. The correlation research design was adopted and secondary panel data collected from annual financial statements. Classical regression and descriptive statistics were used to analyze the data. The study revealed that there was positive and significant effect of internet banking on commercial banks' performance in Italy. Further, internet banking impacted negatively on commercial banks risk levels.

Chipeta and Muthinja (2018) investigated the effect of financial innovations on commercial banks performance in Kenya. Specifically, the study examined the effect of internet banking, mobile banking, agency banking and ATM banking on commercial banks performance. Secondary panel data was gathered from annual financial statements. Koyck dynamic distributed lag model was fitted. It was found that financial innovation had a significant contribution to financial performance. Time-specific characteristics had significant contribution to financial performance as compared to industry characteristics. Since there were only 42 commercial banks in Kenya it was appropriate to consider data for long periods of time to alleviate challenges associated with small samples while analyzing panel data.

Arif, Khan and Iqbal (2013) investigated the effect of bank size on commercial banks' performance in Pakistan. The panel research design was adopted and quarterly secondary data collected for period 2005 to 2009. Univariate and bivariate data were used to analyze the data. It was found that bank size had positive and significant effect on profitability of commercial banks. These findings cannot be generalized in Kenya owing to different state of business environment and economic development. Further, failure to report panel diagnostic tests increased likelihood of reporting biased findings.

Muhindi and Ngaba (2018) examined the effect of bank size on commercial banks' performance in Kenya. The panel research design was adopted. Secondary data was collected from annual financial statements. Ordinary least squares model was fitted. Study findings revealed positive and significant effect of bank size on commercial banks' performance.

Sreesha (2014) examined the effect of firm size, operational efficiency and financial performance in India. The panel research design was adopted and secondary data for 2009 to 2013. Classical regression modelling was applied to analyze the data. It was found that there was positive and significant effect of firm size on financial performance of commercial banks.

Terrazza (2017) examined the effect of bank size on the financial performance of commercial banks in Europe. A secondary of 1270 commercial banks between 2005 to 2012 was collected. A fixed-effects regression model was fitted in addition to descriptive statistics. It was found that firm size had significant effect on commercial bank financial performance.

Conceptual Framework

A conceptual framework can be perceived as logical flow of interaction amongst study variables (Kombo & Tromp, 2009). The direct and moderating effect of bank size on relationship between financial deepening and financial innovations is conceptualized in Figure 2.1.

Independent variables

Moderating variable

Dependent Variable

Figure 2.1 Conceptual Framework

Research Methodology

Research Design

Research is the schematic flow of how the study will be executed to achieve study objectives (Sekaran & Bougie, 2013). This study adopted expo facto research design that sought to examine the relationship between financial innovation adoption and financial deepening of listed commercial banks in Kenya.

Target Population

The target population is total collection of all respondents under consideration (Sekaran & Bougie, 2013). Currently, they are 12 listed commercial banks in Kenya and all were considered in the study. Secondary data

was collected from annual banking report prepared by Central Bank of Kenya on annual basis and from annual banking survey reports.

Data Processing and Analysis

Data collected were analyzed through use of descriptive statistics such as mean, standard deviation, kurtosis and skewness and inferential statistics such as regression and correlation analysis. Moderation was examined through use of stepwise regression modelling and partial differentiation to examine marginal contribution of bank size. The multiple regression model for the study were:

$$Y_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{1it} + \beta_2 X_{2it} + \beta_3 X_{3it} + \beta_4 X_{4it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots \text{Equation 3.1}$$

$$Y_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{1it} + \beta_2 X_{2it} + \beta_3 X_{3it} + \beta_4 X_{4it} + \beta_5 Z_{it} + \beta_6 X_{1it} Z_{it} + \beta_7 X_{2it} Z_{it} + \beta_8 X_{3it} Z_{it} + \beta_9 X_{4it} Z_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots \text{Equation 3.2}$$

Where;

- Y_{it} represent Financial Deepening of Commercial banks
- X_{1it} represent Mobile phone banking (MB) for bank i in period t;
- X_{2it} represent ATM banking (ATMB) for bank i in period t;
- X_{3it} represent Online banking for bank i in period t;
- X_{4it} represent Agency banking for bank i in period t;
- Z_{it} represent Bank size for bank i in period t
- X_{it}*Z_{it} represent the interaction between the respective independent variable with bank size for bank i in period t.

Findings and Discussion

4.1 Descriptive Statistics for Listed Commercial Banks in Kenya

Commercial banks were classified into listed and non-listed and their extent of financial innovations was examined. Findings in Table 4.1 summarized descriptive statistics of listed commercial banks. On average financial deepening of listed commercial banks was 16.03, with a minimum of -25.21 and maximum of 48.28, this depicted wide variations on their extent of financial deepening. The average mobile banking of listed commercial banks was 15.97, with standard deviation of 4.69. ATM banking averaged at 18.18, with minimum of 1.64 and maximum of 28.85, online banking averaged at 19.43 with maximum of 30.19 and minimum of 2.98. Agency banking had an average of 19.39 with minimum of 1.17 and maximum of 32.17. Amongst banking financial innovations, the highest volatile innovation was online banking (standard deviation, 5.07) and least was ATM banking (standard deviation, 4.23). This depicts most listed banks had adopted ATM banking as compared to online banking. The average banking size was 19.63, with minimum of 12.56 and maximum of 36.96. The data was not normally distributed as indicated by Jarque Berra coefficient with p value less than 0.05; this presented enough evidence to warrant rejection of the null hypothesis which stated that the data was normally distributed.

These findings supported Mwangi (2013), Adreniran (2014) and Ngumi (2014) who reported that financial innovations were adopted by commercial banks in Kenya to aid in provision of banking services. Increased access to banking is possible through technological innovation if alternative banking services are easier to use and are more secure as advocated for by technology advancement model.

Table 4.1 Descriptive Statistics for Listed Commercial Banks in Kenya

	Financial Deepening	Mobile Banking	ATM Banking	Online Banking	Agency Banking	Bank Size
Mean	16.03	15.97	18.18	19.43	19.39	19.63
Median	14.94	14.64	18.71	21.89	20.44	19.22
Maximum	48.28	30.30	28.85	30.19	32.17	36.96
Minimum	-25.21	4.24	1.64	2.98	1.17	12.56
Std. Dev.	11.10	4.69	4.23	5.07	4.79	3.23
Skewness	0.22	1.24	-1.14	-0.73	-1.19	3.20
Kurtosis	6.64	4.55	7.73	3.33	6.25	17.25
Jarque-Bera	33.53	21.41	68.91	5.64	40.65	610.10
Probability	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.06	0.00	0.00
Sum	961.64	958.39	1090.52	1165.66	1163.34	1178.09
Sum Sq. Dev.	7270.88	1298.86	1055.91	1517.18	1351.16	614.36
Observations	60	60	60	60	60	60

4.1.1 Trend Analysis for Listed Commercial Banks in Kenya

Pictorial presentation in Figure 4.1, revealed that financial deepening amongst commercial banks had different trends with most listed banks registering upward trends with only a few who had downward trend in 2016. This may imply commercial banks responded negatively to capping of interest rates. Mobile banking uptake amongst listed banks had differing trends, with some banks reporting positive and other negative patterns within period under examination. ATM banking had irregular patterns within period under examination, though downward spiral was noted in 2016. Online banking had irregular patterns with upward and downward spirals though in 2016 there was notable downward spiral. Agency banking recorded upward and downward patterns and banking size grew in different patterns amongst listed banks.

Figure 4.1 Trend Analysis for Listed Commercial Banks in Kenya

4.2 Diagnostic Tests

4.2.1 Panel Unit Root for Listed Commercial Banks in Kenya

The null hypothesis for unit roots stated that there was unit root (the data was not stationary). Study findings in Table 4.2 revealed that there was enough evidence to warrant rejection of the null hypothesis at a 5 percent level of significance since all p values were less than 0.05. Thus, we conclude that financial deepening, mobile banking, ATM banking, online banking, agency banking and bank size of listed commercial banks in Kenya were stationary at levels. Consequently, regression modelling without lagging was fitted with no likelihood of fitting spurious model. There was no need for lagging prior to fitting regression model since the findings concurred with Tarus and Omandi (2013) and Githira et al. (2019b), who found panel data of listed companies to be stationary at levels.

Table 4.2 Panel Unit Root for Listed Commercial Banks in Kenya

Variable	Test	Statistic	P value
Financial deepening	Inverse Chi-squared	64.0374	0.0000
	Inverse Normal	-4.8448	0.0000
	Inverse logit	-5.3217	0.0000
	Modified Inverse chi-squared	6.9629	0.0000
Mobile banking	Inverse Chi-squared	107.0105	0.0000
	Inverse Normal	-3.5206	0.0000
	Inverse logit	-7.7561	0.0000
	Modified Inverse chi-squared	13.7576	0.0000
ATM banking	Inverse Chi-squared	106.3522	0.0000
	Inverse Normal	-4.1693	0.0000
	Inverse logit	-8.1690	0.0000
	Modified Inverse chi-squared	13.6535	0.0000
Online banking	Inverse Chi-squared	111.9973	0.0000
	Inverse Normal	-5.3041	0.0000
	Inverse logit	-9.3452	0.0000
	Modified Inverse chi-squared	14.5460	0.0000
Agency banking	Inverse Chi-squared	27.2511	0.0000
	Inverse Normal	-9.1810	0.0000
	Inverse logit	-8.6046	0.0000
	Modified Inverse chi-squared	11.4065	0.0000
Bank size	Inverse Chi-squared	110.0905	0.0000
	Inverse Normal	-4.1621	0.0000
	Inverse logit	-8.5879	0.0000
	Modified Inverse chi-squared	14.2446	0.0000

4.2.2 Multicollinearity Test for Listed Commercial Banks in Kenya

Results shown in Table 4.3 revealed that there was no collinearity since the highest VIF was 4.05 and minimum 1.59. This implied that a significant joint relationship between mobile banking, ATM banking, online banking and agency banking could be fitted amongst listed commercial banks in Kenya. It was concluded that financial innovations in listed commercial could be jointly evaluated on their influence on financial deepening since VIF and tolerance were within acceptable limits (Baltagi, 2005).

Table 4.3 Multicollinearity Test for Listed Commercial Banks in Kenya

	Collinearity Statistics	
	VIF	Tolerance
Mobile Banking	1.59	0.63
ATM Banking	2.77	0.36
Online banking	2.09	0.48
Agency Banking	4.05	0.25

4.2.3 Correlation Analysis for Listed Commercial Banks in Kenya

Correlation analysis on the relationship between financial innovations and financial deepening of listed commercial banks in Kenya is presented in Table 4.4. It was found that mobile banking had strong positive relationship with financial deepening ($\rho = 0.7632$, p value <0.05). Secondly, ATM banking had strong positive relationship with financial deepening amongst listed banks ($\rho = 0.7260$, p value <0.05). Thirdly, there was a strongly positive and significant relationship between online banking and financial deepening of listed banks ($\rho = 0.6985$, p value <0.05). Fourthly, there was strong positive relationship between agency banking and financial deepening of listed banks in Kenya ($\rho = 0.7683$, p value <0.05). Bank size had strong positive relationship with financial deepening of banks in Kenya ($\rho = 0.7448$, p value <0.05).

These findings disagreed with Hasan et al. (2012) who reported the inverse effect of internet banking on banking penetration. The study concurred with Kingori and Gekara (2015) and Mbugua and Omagwa (2017), who reported positive and significant relationship between agency banking and market penetration of commercial banks. These results supported innovations diffusion theory since adoption of technology has trickled down effect on financial deepening.

Table 4.4 Correlation Analysis for Listed Commercial Banks in Kenya

	Financial Deepening	Mobile Banking	ATM Banking	Online Banking	Agency Banking	Bank size
Financial Deepening	1					
Mobile Banking	0.7632	1				
	0.0000	-----				
ATM Banking	0.7260	0.5500	1			
	0.0000	0.0000	-----			
Online Banking	0.6985	0.4575	0.5684	1		
	0.0000	0.0002	0.0000	-----		
Agency Banking	0.7683	0.5938	0.3691	0.2173	1	
	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	-----	
Bank Size	0.7448	0.6587	0.4655	0.4589	0.5187	1
	0.0000	0.0000	0.0002	0.0002	0.0000	-----

4.2.4 Panel Heteroskedasticity for Listed Commercial Banks in Kenya

For listed commercial banks, study findings revealed that the data was not homoscedastic as indicated by Chi square values of 37.95 and 100.58 and p values <0.05, for non-moderated and moderated regression models. Due to this robust standard error were used instead of normal standard errors, this was in line with (Woodridge, 2012).

Table 4.5 Panel Heteroskedasticity for Listed Commercial Banks in Kenya

Model	χ^2 -Value	P value
Without Moderation	37.95	0.00
With Moderation	100.58	0.00

4.2.5 Serial Panel Correlation for Listed Commercial Banks in Kenya

First order serial correlation test amongst listed commercial banks test in Table 4.6 had p value greater than 0.05 for moderated and non-moderated models. This indicated the absence of first order serial correlation, thus no need to fit FGLS. These results agreed with (Wanjau, Muturi & Ngumi, 2018), who reported absence of first order serial correlation amongst listed companies in East Africa securities exchange. They contrasted (Muchiri, Muturi & Ngumi, 2016) who reported presence of first order correlation on their examination on the effect of financial structure on financial performance of listed companies in East Africa Securities Exchanges.

Table 4.6 Panel Serial Correlation for Listed Commercial Banks in Kenya

Model	F-Value	P value
Without Moderation	0.263	0.523
With Moderation	0.868	0.756

4.2.6 Panel Granger Causality Test for Listed Commercial Banks in Kenya

Granger causality was applied to evaluate causality between banking financial innovations and the financial deepening of listed banks in Kenya. Results shown in Table 4.7, indicated that there was no causality between mobile banking and financial deepening, ATM banking and financial deepening, online banking and financial deepening, agency banking and financial deepening. Further there was no causality between mobile banking, ATM banking, online banking and agency banking, respectively. Bank size had no causality with financial deepening. In addition, there was unidirectional causality between mobile banking and bank size.

Table 4.7 Panel Granger Causality Test for Listed Commercial Banks in Kenya

Null Hypothesis:	F-Statistic	Prob.
Mobile banking does not Granger Cause financial deepening	1.8550	0.1715
Financial deepening does not Granger Cause mobile banking	2.4337	0.1024
ATM banking does not Granger Cause financial deepening	0.2340	0.7926
Financial deepening does not Granger Cause ATM banking	0.9681	0.3898
Online banking does not Granger Cause financial deepening	0.1163	0.8906
Financial deepening does not Granger Cause online banking	1.5476	0.2270
Agency banking does not Granger Cause financial deepening	0.3345	0.7180
Financial deepening does not Granger Cause agency banking	0.1166	0.8903
Bank size does not Granger Cause financial deepening	1.2710	0.2932
Financial deepening does not Granger Cause bank size	0.0103	0.9898
ATM banking does not Granger Cause mobile banking	0.8355	0.4421
Mobile banking does not Granger Cause ATM banking	0.8095	0.4532
Online banking does not Granger Cause mobile banking	0.0290	0.9714
Mobile banking does not Granger Cause online banking	0.9458	0.3981
Agency banking does not Granger Cause mobile banking	0.9140	0.4103
Mobile banking does not Granger Cause agency banking	0.3917	0.6788
Bank size does not Granger Cause mobile banking	6.6973	0.0034
Mobile banking does not Granger Cause bank size	1.7923	0.1815
Online banking does not Granger Cause ATM banking	0.5556	0.5787
ATM banking does not Granger Cause online banking	0.0044	0.9956
Agency banking does not Granger Cause ATM banking	0.1115	0.8949
ATM banking does not Granger Cause agency banking	0.0475	0.9537
Bank size does not Granger Cause ATM banking	0.6102	0.5489
ATM banking does not Granger Cause bank size	0.0061	0.9939
Agency banking does not Granger Cause online banking	0.3117	0.7342
Online banking does not Granger Cause agency banking	0.4097	0.6670
Bank size does not Granger Cause online banking	0.9632	0.3916
Online banking does not Granger Cause bank size	0.1134	0.8932
Bank size does not Granger Cause agency banking	0.8650	0.4299
Agency banking does not Granger Cause bank size	0.2055	0.8152

4.2.7 Panel Hausman Test for Listed Commercial Banks in Kenya

As shown in Table 4.8, Chi square statistics was 4.9439 and p value of 0.2931 which was greater than 0.05. Consequently, there was enough evidence to warrant rejection of the null hypothesis and conclusion that the most appropriate model to examine the relationship between banking financial innovations and financial deepening of listed banks in Kenya was random effects. These findings agreed with Muchiri et al. (2016), who adopted the random-effects model and they concurred with Kariuki (2017) on examination on effect of firm characteristics on efficiency of savings and credit cooperative societies of Kenya.

Table 4.8 Panel Hausman Test for Listed Commercial Banks in Kenya

Test Summary		Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
		4.9439	4	0.2931
Variable	Fixed	Random	Var (Diff.)	Prob.
Mobile Banking	1.2427	1.0280	0.0219	0.1472
ATM Banking	0.6631	0.5904	0.0133	0.5283
Online Banking	0.5699	0.6050	0.0265	0.8291
Agency Banking	0.1446	0.3068	0.0299	0.3483

4.3 Relationship between Commercial Banking Financial Innovations and Financial Deepening of Listed Commercial Banks in Kenya

Multiple regression analysis revealed that banking innovations had a significant relationship with financial deepening ($F = 51.5826$, p value < 0.05). An R squared of 0.7895 indicated that mobile banking, ATM banking,

online banking and agency banking explained 78.95 percent of changed in financial deepening could be jointly explained by banking innovations while the remaining percentage can be accounted for by other attributes excluded in the model amongst listed banks.

The first hypothesis stated that mobile banking had no significant relationship with financial deepening. Results in Table 4.68 revealed a positive and significant relationship between mobile banking and the financial deepening of commercial banks in Kenya ($\beta = 1.0280$, p value <0.05). This implied that unit increase in mobile banking increased financial deepening by 0.8903 while holding constant ATM, online and agency banking in listed banks.

The second hypothesis stated that ATM banking had no significant relationship with financial deepening. It was found that ATM banking had a significant positive relationship financial deepening of commercial banks in Kenya ($\beta = 0.5904$, p value <0.05). This implied that unit increase in ATM banking increased financial deepening by 0.5904 while holding constant mobile, online and agency banking in listed banks.

The third hypothesis stated that online banking had no significant relationship with financial deepening. It was found that online banking had a significant positive relationship financial deepening of commercial banks in Kenya ($\beta = 0.6050$, p value <0.05). This implied that unit increase in online banking increased financial deepening by 0.3050 while holding constant mobile, ATM and agency banking in listed banks.

The fourth hypothesis stated that agency banking had no significant relationship with financial deepening. It was found that online banking had a significant positive relationship financial deepening of commercial banks in Kenya ($\beta = 0.3068$, p value <0.05). This implied that unit increase in agency banking increased financial deepening by 0.3068 while holding constant mobile, ATM and online banking in listed banks.

$$\text{Financial Deepening} = -28.8245 + 1.0280 * \text{Mobile Banking} + 0.5904 * \text{ATM banking} + 0.6050 * \text{Online banking} + 0.3068 * \text{Agency banking} \dots \dots \dots 4.1$$

Table 4.9 Relationship between Commercial Banking Financial Innovations and Financial Deepening of Listed Commercial Banks in Kenya

Variable	Coefficient	Robust Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-28.8245	3.3145	-8.6965	0.0000
Mobile Banking	1.0280	0.1852	5.5490	0.0000
ATM Banking	0.5904	0.2714	2.1755	0.0339
Online Banking	0.6050	0.1967	3.0762	0.0033
Agency Banking	0.3068	0.2898	1.0587	0.2944
R-squared	0.7895	Mean dependent variable		16.0273
Adjusted R-squared	0.7742	S.D. dependent variable		11.1011
S.E. of regression	5.2747	Sum squared residuals		1530.2410
F-statistic	51.5826	Durbin-Watson stat		2.1011
Prob (F-statistic)	0.0000			

4.4 Moderating Effect of Bank Size on Relationship between Banking Financial Innovations and Financial Deepening of Listed Commercial Banks in Kenya

Regression results in Table 4.10 revealed that 88.76 percent of changes in financial deepening of listed banks were accounted for by mobile, ATM, online, agency banking, bank size, moderated banking financial innovations while the remaining percentage was accounted for by other factors excluded in the model. R squared increased by 9.81 percent (0.8876-0.7895) after moderation, which indicated banking size had moderating effect on the relationship between banking financial innovations and the financial deepening of listed banks in Kenya. Further, bank size had significant positive effect on financial deepening of commercial banks in Kenya ($\beta = 0.5958$, p value <0.05).

After bank size moderation on mobile banking, MB*BS there was positive not significant relationship with financial deepening ($\beta = 0.0111$, p value >0.05). Secondly, bank size had positive non-significant moderating effect on ATM banking, ATMB*BS ($\beta = 0.0068$, p value >0.05). Thirdly, online banking had positive and non-significant moderation on bank size ($\beta = 0.0088$, p value >0.05). Finally, bank size had positive non-significant moderating effect on agency bank, AB*BS ($\beta = 0.0084$, p value >0.05).

Financial Deepening = -26.1387 + 0.1670 * Mobile banking + 0.3139 * ATM banking+ 0.3269* Online banking + 0.0724*Agency banking + 0.5958 * Bank size + 0.0111*MB*BS + 0.0068 * ATMB*BS+0.0160*OB*BS+0.0084*AB*BS..... (4.3)

Bank size moderating effect was confirmed through comparison of moderated and non-moderated coefficients with marginal change of banking innovations on financial deepening of commercial banks in Kenya. Bank size moderating effect will be present if marginalized coefficients will differ from non-moderated banking innovations coefficients. The following equations were adopted:

$$\frac{\delta FDi,t}{\delta Mbi,t} = \beta_1 + \beta_6 BS = 0.1670 + 0.0111 * 19.63 = 0.3849$$

$$\frac{\delta FDi,t}{\delta ATMBi,t} = \beta_2 + \beta_7 BS = 0.3139 + 0.0068 * 19.63 = 0.4474$$

$$\frac{\delta FDi,t}{\delta OBi,t} = \beta_3 + \beta_8 BS = 0.23269 + 0.0088 * 19.63 = 0.4054$$

$$\frac{\delta FDi,t}{\delta ABi,t} = \beta_4 + \beta_9 BS = 0.0724 + 0.0084 * 19.63 = 0.2373$$

Comparison between marginalized coefficients and those in equation 4.1 (Financial Deepening = -28.8245 + 1.0280 * Mobile Banking + 0.5904 * ATM banking + 0.6050 * Online banking + 0.3068 * Agency banking), these coefficients differed. Consequently, it can be concluded that bank size had moderating effect on relationship between banking financial innovations and financial deepening of listed commercial banks in Kenya.

Table 4.10 Moderating Effect of Bank Size on Relationship between Banking Financial Innovations and Financial Deepening of Listed Commercial Banks in Kenya

Variable	Coefficient	Robust Std. Err.	Z	P>z	
Mobile banking	0.1670	0.1992	0.8400	0.4020	
ATM banking	0.3139	0.2262	1.3900	0.1650	
Online banking	0.3269	0.1788	1.8300	0.0680	
Agency banking	0.0724	0.2491	0.2900	0.7710	
Banking size	0.5958	0.2498	2.3900	0.0170	
MB*BS	0.0111	0.0073	1.5300	0.1260	
ATM*BS	0.0068	0.0097	0.7000	0.4840	
OB*BS	0.0088	0.0101	0.8700	0.3840	
AB*BS	0.0084	0.0102	0.8200	0.4110	
Constant	-26.1387	4.7048	-5.5600	0.0000	
R-sq: within = 0.8843		between = 0.9085	overall = 0.8876	Wald chi ² (9) =394.81	Prob > chi ² =0.000

Conclusion and Recommendations

The mobile banking concept is in the positive trend towards full realization of financial deepening in its full impact. Hence, the Government must develop better policies to manage this subsector, which has the potential to be a very high-volume financial transaction platform. Since mobile banking may overstep and overtake some commercial banking functions, there is need to regulate and rehabilitate it to its main objective of remittances. The Government should also make it compulsory for every mobile network company to participate in this product to reduce costs for consumers though there is need for its independent regulation.

There is a need for banking companies to improve securities on use of debit and credit cards to execute online purchases and payments. This would minimize financial fraud associated with unauthorized access personal credit card information. Alternative security approaches beyond use of personal identification numbers, biometric identification should be incorporated during ATM banking transactions.

Although online banking services have received positive reception, it is faced by several security threats. Customer’s sensitization against the use of public internet services, this would minimize possibilities of financial losses. Banking institutions should develop financial services that can be easily accessed through use internet instead of traditional approaches. This would save on environmental degradation and eliminate wastages.

From the findings, over the period agency banking has been in operation, the kind of service offered by the agents has been limited to simple transactions and supportive functions like deposits and withdrawals. A more interesting perspective will be when banks allow agents to perform core activities like vetting loan applications and collecting loan repayment, it is recommended that the banks transfer the basic knowledge to the agents to enable them to perform these extra activities. The banks also need to advertise the other kinds of services that can be done via agency banking to ensure an uptake of all services offered by agents who will be more efficient and cost effective.

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